

FLOW ORIENTATION OF VEGETABLE FIBRES

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SUMMARY: Vegetable fibres are attracting more and more interest because of chances they offer to reinforce plastics. Many studies are being done in order to determine their real potential as reinforcing phase in plastic composites. The aim of this work is to verify the effectiveness of the reinforcement, by comparing the performance of a wood-plastic composite with different fibre layouts. Several techniques for orienting elementary vegetable fibres in one direction were developed to produce unidirectional wood/plastic composites. The efficiency of these techniques was appreciated by optical- and S.E.M.- micrographic examinations of the composite cross-section and fracture surfaces, and it was evaluated by mechanically testing samples of a 0°-oriented, a random and a 90°-oriented composite plate. One of the alignment techniques produced the best results as far as orientation is concerned. The 0°-oriented unidirectional composite samples showed the best flexural properties.

KEYWORDS: vegetable fibres, short fibre orientation.

INTRODUCTION

The need of mechanically reinforcing polymeric materials led to designing and producing fibrous composites. Good performances of some kinds of fibres, such as carbon, kevlar and glass, allowed fully replacing metals in aeronautics and aerospace applications [1]. However, these materials gave birth to some problems, which are still unsolved. Commercially, the first problem is cost: it is very high, so that competition with conventional materials is very hard. In addition, they are definitely non-biodegradable, and the presence of cited fibres in a polymeric matrix makes recycling procedures more difficult.

Natural fibres based composite materials began to be studied in the first half of this century. At present, many reasons justify experimenters' interest in them: they are low cost materials, fibre properties are very good (especially their properties-to-weight ratios), fibres are biodegradable and health-safe.

Studying the design and production of natural fibre composites, almost all problems connected with composite materials have to be faced. Fibre extraction is made by old and inadequate methods with regard to composites production needs. Since fibres are single vegetable dead cells [2,3], they are structurally short fibres, carrying all those design-related problems connected with short fibres [4]. The load-transfer problem is one of the most serious these fibres have got, as their adhesion capability to polymer matrices is very poor [5,6]. The very peculiar fibre structure makes fabrication processes have strong limits [7]. Applications of these composites still are very few: wide use in structures is impossible at present.

In order to start fully understanding the great potential of natural vegetable fibres as reinforcing phase in polymeric composites, this work tries to explore the technological potentials of these materials analyzing ways of improving fibre alignment and testing in flexure of aligned 25% in weight-wood fibre/polyester composite. Several techniques for orienting elementary vegetable fibres were studied: two of them, completely new, gave satisfactory results. Flexural properties of the 0°-oriented composite were put in comparison with the responses of a randomly oriented composite and a 90°-oriented one.

Specimen preparation

In this work a polyester resin matrix (thermosetting) was utilized. The resin was supplied by REICHOLD, and the resin type was Norpol 7290. A chemithermomechanical pulp extracted from aspen wood was used as fibrous reinforcement.

Geometrical measurements performed by means of an optical microscope yielded exact dimensions of both cross-section and length of the fibres. Considering that the cylindrical fibre structure collapsed into a ribbon-like one, the cross-section lost the well-known ring shape and assumed a quasi-elliptical shape, whose major axis is about 30 µm long while minor axis is about 10 µm long. With regard to the length, its measured distribution is shown in Figure 1.

Wood pulp was first water impregnated, by letting it lie in complete immersion for at least 24 hours. The second stage consisted of fibre separation, which was reached by means of a water-mixing device, built by adapting a normal column drilling machine with a screw having non-sharp blades.

The treatment time varied in depending on the amount of fibres to separate. The order of magnitude of rate of separation was approximately two hours per gram of wood pulp.

Figure 1: Experimental fibre length distribution

After fibre separation, the alignment stage took place. Several methods were experienced in order to obtain satisfying fibre orientation.

The first technique started by drying fibres. The drying process was conducted by putting the fibres in a 80°C chamber of a laboratory oven. Subsequently a mixture with resin was produced, by putting an amount of fibres of 10 % in weight.

The aim was to produce a fibre orientation by making the mixture pass through a converging pipe.

Although the fibre percentage was so small, the mixture got very high viscosity, so as to make it very difficult to create a suitable flow to allow fibre orientation in any kind of pipe. One of the reasons why the viscosity raised so much was that the fibres were dispersed in the resin with great difficulty, since they always tended to remain joined to each-other. This technique was soon abandoned.

Completely different criteria led to planning other kinds of experiments. The idea was to first obtain an alignment of fibres, so producing a thin layer of oriented fibres. Subsequently the composite had to be built by hand-impregnating the layers with polyester resin.

Two methods were examined to align fibres [8]. Both took advance from the utilization of two close-packed filter screens with different mesh-sizes. Both filters played the role of fibre collecting screens.

A mixture of elementary fibres and water was used as a sort of precursor, as water allows fibres keeping well separated from each-other.

The first method consisted of a rotating cylinder, whose surface consisted of one of the filter screens (Fig. 2). Two rotational speeds of 140 and 180 rpm were adopted. The orienting flow was created by a converging hole linked to a container carrying the water/fibres mixture. The mixture was pushed out from the container through the converging hole by the hydrostatic pressure of the fluid level in the container. The level was kept constant by continuously adding new mixture.

The converging hole was able to yield the orientation of fibres, since single fibres were observed to be perfectly following the water flow in any condition. The flow direction at the end of the converging hole was kept radial with respect to the cylindrical screen. Fibres were deposited on the screen in the form of an almost totally oriented layer.

Figure 2: Scheme of the first method apparatus used in fibre alignment

The main problem connected with this method was that it was impossible to make the oriented fibres deposition rate raise up to reach a useful consistence of the layer, in order to make it handily. Anyway, the filter with largest holes yielded the best results. With regard to the orientation of fibres, a higher rotation speed yielded better results.

In the second method, the filters, having a circular shape, were put in a horizontal position, anchoring their central point to a rotating, impermeable disk (Fig.3). The radius of the filters was higher than the radius of the disk, so that two zone were obtained on the rotational plane: the first

was impermeable as for the presence of the disk under the filter and the second, ring shaped, was peripheral and permeable. A rotational speed of 140 rpm was adopted.

By keeping the filters and the cylindrical support in rotation, the first step of the procedure was to spill the mixture from the container, letting it fall down on the filter surface in the central zone of the filter near the anchoring point (Fig.3). Afterwards, pure water was also let falling down on the central zone of the filter surface.

The spiral water flow from the central point towards more peripheral positions due to centrifugal forces, resulted in fibre orientation along the flow direction within the impermeable zone.

As soon as the flow went beyond the central impermeable zone into the peripheral permeable zone, the water could run through the filter leaving the fibres laying in a direction tangential to the circumference of the support, so configuring a planar ring.

The result of this process is a thin and narrow ring-shaped ribbon of fibres mainly oriented tangentially to the circumferences of the ring.

The circumference radius of the support had to be enlarged enough to reach a satisfying alignment.

Figure 3: Scheme of the second method apparatus used in fibre alignment

Best results in the fibre alignment were found when using the greater mesh-size filter screen. This is explained by considering that it allows water to be expelled more easily from the mixture.

After the orientation stage, quasi-linear portions of the ring-shaped ribbon of fibres was dried and impregnated by hand, to produce composite samples with fibres oriented to 0° and 90° of standard dimensions.

Optical microscopy analysis showed the existence of highly oriented regions, but less oriented regions were also present. An aligned region is showed in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Optical micrograph of an aligned fibre layer

Mechanical tests

In order to quantify the orientation effect and to evaluate the efficacy of the alignment technique, flexural tests were conducted by means of an Instron universal machine, mod. 1251. All tests were made under standard conditions, following the ASTM D790M Standard for flexural testing of composites. Three different kinds of samples were produced and tested: randomly oriented, longitudinally aligned (0°) and orthogonally aligned (90°) plates.

Table 1 gives evidence of increased mechanical properties of the resin in case of 0°-aligned reinforcement with respect to the random composite and even more with respect of the orthogonally oriented one.

	Flexural modules (Gpa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Maximum strain (%)
random	3,9	95	0.031
0°- aligned	4,9	137	0.037
90°- aligned	2,7	53	0.023
Aspen[9,10]	8-7	60-70	

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the different materials

Figure 5 shows the stress-strain diagrams of the three composites. It can be noticed that energy needed to break the longitudinally aligned composite is larger than the energy involved in the breakage of the other two kinds of samples.

Figure 5: Stress-Strain diagram of the three materials

Figure 6: S.E.M. micrograph of the unidirectional composite structure

Evidence of the fibre alignment is given by the S.E.M. analysis of fracture surface of the composite under flexural load (Fig. 6).

Conclusion

In this work, an aligned vegetable fibre/polymer composite has been produced. In order to make it, layers of highly oriented fibres were first obtained, by using a new technique based on the flow of a fibre/water mixture upon the surface of a close-packed filter screen. Aligned layers were then hand impregnated. In order to evaluate the alignment quality and to verify the effectiveness of the aligned fibre reinforcement of the polyester matrix, flexural tests of the composite mechanical properties were carried out. Test results showed the existence of noticeable advantages yielded by the alignment method. However, it needs considerable improvement, especially as far as optimization is concerned: the process parameters need to be studied in order to gain best results.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Crivelli Visconti, "Overview of composites: their uses and technology trends" *Polymer Plastics Technology & Engineering*, Vol.31 (1992) p.1.
- [2] H.L. Bos, M.J.A. van den Oever, O.C.J.J. Peters, "Structure-property relations of annual fibres and their influence on composite properties" *Proceedings of ECCM-8, Naples (1998)*.
- [3] E.T.N. Bisanda, L.Y. Mwaikambo, "The performance of kapok/cotton fabric fibre reinforced composites" *Proceedings of the Workshop on Textiles, Arusha (Tanzania)*, (1997).
- [4] R.T. Woodhams, G. Thomas, D.K. Rodgers, "Wood Fibres as Reinforcing Fillers for Polyolefins" *Polym. Eng. & Sci.*, Vol. **24** (1984) p. 1166.
- [5] J.M. Felix, P. Gatenholm, "The Nature of Adhesion in Composites of Modified Cellulose Fibers and Polypropylene" *J. of Appl. Polym. Sci.*, Vol. **42** (1991) p. 609.
- [6] D. Maldas, B.V. Kokta, C. Daneault, "Influence of Couplung Agents and Treatments on the Mechanical Properties of Cellulose Fiber-Polystyrene Composites" *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. **37** (1989) p.751.
- [7] K.L. Yam, B.K. Gogoi, C.C. Lai, S.E. Selke, "Composites From Compounding Wood Fibres With Recycled High Density Polyethylene" *Polym. Eng. & Sci.*, Vol.**30** (1990) p. 693.
- [8] Patent pending.
- [9] Manuale dell'ingegnere Nuovo Colombo, Vol.1, sez. C, Ulrico Hoepli, Milano.
- [10] F. Wangaard, *The mechanical properties of wood*, John Wiley & sons, Inc., New York Chapman & Hall, limited, London.

